

IMPROVING THE PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITIES OF FUTURE TEACHERS IN FOREIGN TEACHING METHODOLOGY.

Sabokhat Rixsibayevna Djalilova,

Senior Lecturer, Uzbekistan State University
of Physical Education and Sports

ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to the importance of self-sufficient elements of multilevel professional training in the methodology of foreign languages teaching. The authors define the role of self-sufficient elements of multilevel vocational training in the modern education system and to the methods of teaching German as a foreign language. The author considers the characteristic of linguoculturology suggested by the majority of scientists. The ways of overcoming foreign literature difficulties are considered.

Keywords: language, culture, linguoculturology, text, foreign language, training.

Indicators of readiness for professional activity cannot be considered as isolated, self-contained elements of multi-level professional training. The whole point of the proposed readiness indicators, all requirements for them should proceed from the idea that any readiness indicators should be elements of a complete system. The purpose of creating indicators is to develop them as one of the components of the system, to give a clearer focus to all teacher training. In this regard, the development of indicators of readiness for professional activity should proceed from a number of principles.

First, indicators of readiness of a specialist in the field of education should contribute to the preservation of a single educational space in the Republic of Uzbekistan and the entry of the national system into the world system of pedagogical education.

Secondly, the indicators created should make it possible to determine the specialist's readiness for constantly changing professional activities, i.e. it is necessary to develop such indicators, which, evaluating it in accordance with the real goals of education at the moment, provided a double lead in relation to the social order of today.

Thirdly, the level of readiness of specialists in the field of education should be determined on the basis of solving specially developed professional tasks. Differences in the implementation of standards can be expressed in the way educational and vocational training is carried out. There may be two options for the ratio of these programs, which are important to consider when developing indicators of specialist readiness.

The requirements for educational activities are unusually dynamic and in essence are one of the most difficult historical categories subject to constant change. Therefore, the second of the above-mentioned principles for developing specialist readiness indicators turns out to be very important and involves mandatory determination of readiness both in terms of the goals of today's education and in terms of the requirements that will be presented to a specialist in the near and far future. Indeed, today's teacher must be trained so that he can foster an active, active member of society in the conditions of both today and tomorrow, adjusted for the constant acceleration of the process of socio-historical development of society. Undoubtedly, it is equally important to keep in mind those socio-historical changes that constantly occur with each person: their social role, needs and requirements change, and the social value of each person increases. An education specialist should be prepared to take these changes into account. In numerous psychological and pedagogical studies it is stated that any human activity is essentially an activity for solving problems. That is why the third principle underlying the development of the indicators under consideration is the provision according to which it is advisable to determine the level of specialist readiness based on solving problems inherent in this type of activity.

The fourth principle is an objective assessment of readiness for pedagogical activity on the basis of a qualitative and quantitative analysis of solving problems, since the process of solving implies:

- Mandatory definition of activity objectives;
- Targeted application of knowledge and skills in their unity, in strict accordance with the problem posed in this task;
- Use of experience acquired in the learning process in a specific pedagogical situation. It is important to analyze and assess the level of solution of each task according to the following criteria: the degree of compliance of the proposed solution to the problem posed the level of analysis of all the components of the problem condition, the degree of variability when making a decision, the degree of evidence of a decision. Assessment of the readiness of a specialist on the basis of his mastering

the functions characteristic of this professional activity is the following, fifth principle, which must be guided in determining readiness indicators. It is known that diagnostic, informational, constructive-design, organizational, communicative, prognostic, research and evaluation functions are usually attributed to such functions. However, it is impossible to check the level of mastering these functions without presenting the structure of each of them in the form of operational components, since only when the operational structure of all functions is defined, professional pedagogical tasks can be made to assess the level of preparedness for real activity. The need to develop and actually use the indicators of readiness for professional activity at all stages of preparation for it is determined by two points: first, the level of readiness, which at each previous stage in one way or another predetermines the possibility of more or less successful advancement at the next stages; secondly, knowledge of the features of readiness at the early stages, which will allow to build a pedagogical influence at the subsequent stages so as to ensure optimal progress. In addition, since the essence of any educational process is the process of cognition, when implementing this principle, it is advisable to take into account the well-known position of S. Rubinshtein, according to which the cognitive process goes from general, undifferentiated synthesis to differentiated analysis and then to authentic synthesis that summarizes all that that revealed in the analysis. This provision is important to consider when determining the specific content of educational and professional tasks. Realizing the latter principle, it should be borne in mind that the proposed educational and professional tasks should be available to solve at any stage of continuing pedagogical education, and at the same time they should be designed to represent the possibility of solving them at different levels: from the level of common sense to the level high professionalism. Only in this case it will be possible, on the one hand, to see the process of becoming a specialist, and on the other - to reveal the specific features of solving educational and professional tasks at each stage of continuing pedagogical education. Consequently, uniform requirements for the construction of tasks should not exclude, but imply a certain differentiation of them at all levels and stages of the system of continuous pedagogical education. Based on the study of psychological and pedagogical literature, we can single out the following indicators (criteria) of teacher readiness for professional activity.

1. Understanding the social role and functions of the teacher in modern society.
2. The presence of socially significant motives for the choice of the profession of a teacher and the pedagogical ideal.

3. The depth of mastering the concepts of professional honor, professional duty, a sense of belonging to the teacher and pride in their profession. 4. Aspiration and high professional level of mastering: psychological and pedagogical knowledge; special knowledge; professional skills; degree of real possession of them at different levels of training.

5. The presence of the need for pedagogical communication with children, the level of communication culture, the development of real forms of manifestation of this need. The degree of ownership of active forms and types of educational activities and practical participation in it.

6. The presence and dynamics of personal professionally significant qualities: requirements, pedagogical dignity, competence, professional responsibility, etc.

7. The degree of manifestation and the level of practical knowledge of the system-forming function of the pedagogical work - organizational.

9. The presence and dynamics of the need for professional self-education and self-education. On the organic connection of the content of the phenomena of professional competence and readiness to professional activity indicates the fact that they have a number of common elements. In particular, knowledge and skills (subject, generally didactic, psychological, and methodological) are the core of readiness and at the same time components of the teacher's professional competence.

The success of performing any activity requires a certain pool of knowledge and skills, which is the foundation of a person's professional competence. It is on the basis of special professional knowledge and skills that the person creates a "... special mental state, such as the presence in the subject of an image of a structure of a certain action and a constant focus of consciousness on its implementation," called V. A. Slavenin's teacher's readiness for professional activity. Thus, pedagogical competence and professional readiness for practical work are formed as complementary properties of an individual in a single pedagogical process. However, one can judge about one or another degree of readiness for pedagogical activity only when the person has accumulated the necessary knowledge and skills, which are formed not so much spontaneously but as purposefully and in stages. As the teacher's professional readiness improves, his competence in the field of education rises. Moreover, the increment of readiness occurs practically in the everyday process of pedagogical activity, if they are organized competently, at a high scientific and methodological level. Readiness for professional activity, being a prerequisite for the formation of competence, is improved not only on special, problem courses or advanced training courses, but also in extracurricular activities, during the work of

creative groups, in the course of practical activities, in professional communication with colleagues. They are not only a condition for the formation of competence, but also an indicator of suitability for the professional activity of a teacher. The old ways, where organized, systematic self-education was carried out mainly in various courses, in circles, people's universities, etc., are insufficient. Their place is increasingly being taken by an individual person's independent work on various sources of knowledge, with only a little consultation of specialists from a particular field of science and practice.

REFERENCES:

1. Исаева У., Джалилова С. The usage of new pedagogical technologies in lessons //Молодой ученый. – 2018. – №. 5. – С. 169-171.
2. Богиева Т. Р. Преимущества и недостатки применения традиционных и нетрадиционных методов преподавания иностранного языка в образовательных учреждениях СПО //Инновационная наука. – 2016. – №. 4-2 (16). – С. 139-141.
3. Mahsudova B. H. et al. Проблема межкультурной коммуникации в обучении иностранным языкам //Theoretical & Applied Science. – 2018. – №. 1. – С. 76-79.
4. Жалилова С. Использование лингвокультурологического подхода в обучении иностранным языкам //Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS). – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 3. – С. 64-71.
5. Rixsibayevna D. S. TYPES OF LEARNING ENGLISH METHODS IN SPORT DIRECTION //Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования. – 2024. – Т. 15. – №. 1. – С. 45-49.
6. Rixsibayevna D. S. IMPROVE PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITIES OF FUTURE TEACHERS //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNALI. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 12. – С. 531-534.
7. Rixsibayevna D. S. COMMUNICATIVE-COGNITIVE APPROACH TO TEACHING OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES //World scientific research journal. – 2022. – Т. 4. – №. 1. – С. 198-200.
8. Максудова В. Х., Жалилова С. Р., Нуримова С. Э. КОММУНИКАТИВНО-КОГНИТИВНЫЙ ПОДХОД К ОБУЧЕНИЮ ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ //Путь науки. – 2015. – №. 3. – С. 128-130.